

Negotiating *through* “terrorists”: US-PLO collaboration during the Iran hostage crisis

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Abstract

Few international events had a greater lasting impact on the trajectory of American politics in the late twentieth century than the 1979 Iran hostage crisis. However, most conventional accounts of this 444-day diplomatic disaster overlook the fact that thirteen of the original hostages were released two weeks into captivity. Drawing on declassified US government documents, this article traces the unlikely role the Palestine Liberation Organization played in efforts to resolve the Iran hostage crisis on behalf of the Carter Administration from November 1979 until at least the summer of 1980. Drawing on the international relations literature on alliances, this research thus represents a case study of the conditions under which a violent non-state actor may cooperate with an ideologically opposed government against its own ally. To do so, I first argue that the PLO indisputably negotiated the release of thirteen American hostages from Iran in late November 1979. Second, by evaluating formerly unexamined US State Department Situation Reports, I propose another instance of US-PLO cooperation during the Iran hostage crisis: with the assistance of Archbishop Hilarion Capucci, the PLO likely arranged for release of eight U.S. servicemen's bodies from Iran in May 1980. Ultimately, by analysing Yasser Arafat's actions before and during the Iran hostage crisis, I employ Staniland's framework of armed politics to posit that Arafat's ideological position and tactical interests generated a distinct “political role” he could serve for the United States. Thus, the Palestine Liberation Organization's identity as an anti-Western revolutionary group, alongside its ties to the Iranian opposition movement, made it uniquely positioned to negotiate US interests in post-revolutionary Iran.

Introduction

“Fuck the Shah. I am not going to welcome him here when he has places to go.”¹
– *President Jimmy Carter*

Few international events had a greater lasting impact on the trajectory of American politics in the late 20th century than the Iran hostage crisis. Since 1979, the (in)actions of the Carter administration throughout this 444-day diplomatic disaster have been picked apart and criticized ad nauseum. After the unanticipated success of the Iranian Revolution, the country's now exiled monarch, Mohammad Reza Shah, sought refuge in the United States. When President Carter reluctantly agreed to admit the Shah for cancer treatment, embittered Iranian university students of the self-

¹ Kai Bird, *The Chairman: John J. McCloy and The Making of the American Establishment* (New York: Simon and Schuster, 1992), 648.

proclaimed Muslim Student Followers of the Imam's Line stormed the US Embassy in Tehran on November 4, 1979, holding fifty-two American embassy workers hostage for over a year. The Carter administration's months-long attempt to resolve the crisis through "diplomatic restraint" failed repeatedly. Finally, through a combination of sanctions, frozen asset releases, and Algerian diplomacy, all fifty-two hostages were liberated on January 20th, 1981. That same day, Ronald Reagan was sworn into office as the 40th president of the United States.

Yet, this is an incomplete picture: sixty-six Americans were taken hostage in Tehran in November 1979, not fifty-two. Most conventional accounts of the Iran hostage crisis overlook the release of thirteen of the original hostages taken on November 4th merely two weeks into the crisis. The select sources which mention this early development passively note that "hostages were released" without detailing how, or through whom, the release was coordinated. Why and how, did these thirteen Americans—all women or Black men—come to be liberated more than four hundred days before their colleagues? An actor whose major involvement in the Iran hostage crisis has been overlooked by scholars until recently thus emerges: the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO).

Drawing on declassified government documents, this article traces the unlikely role that the Palestine Liberation Organization played in efforts to resolve the Iran hostage crisis on behalf of the Carter Administration from November 1979 until at least the summer of 1980. With the exception of Norwegian scholar Jørgen Jensehaugen, no academics have examined the PLO's involvement in the Iran hostage crisis until now. Thus, the objectives of this article are twofold: on one level, to contribute to the sparse literature on this improbable US-PLO partnership by chronicling the latter's activity during the Iran hostage crisis; on another, to exemplify how armed organizations engage in different forms of political relationships with the governments they ostensibly oppose or support to fulfil short-term tactical goals.

The analytical crux of this article hinges on two interrelated but distinct claims. First, I argue that the PLO negotiated the release of thirteen American hostages from Iran in late November 1979. Until recently, there was a complete lacuna in the literature on the hostage crisis concerning the PLO's role in negotiation efforts. Though Jensehaugen provides the first detailed analysis of US-PLO collaboration during this period, I go beyond his argument in positing that, first, the PLO not only "seems to have played a significant role in" but indisputably negotiated the release of thirteen American hostages from Iran in late November 1979.² Second, by evaluating formerly unexamined State Department Situation Reports (SITREPs), I provide insight into another instance of US-PLO cooperation from the Iran hostage crisis that scholars have lacked sufficient details to confirm until now: with the help of one eclectic, arms-dealing Archbishop, the PLO plausibly arranged for the bodies of eight U.S. servicemen killed in May 1980 during Operation Eagle Claw to be released from Iran.

Ultimately, by analysing Arafat's actions prior to and during the hostage

² Jørgen Jensehaugen, "A Palestinian Window of Opportunity? The PLO, the US and the Iranian Hostage Crisis," *British Journal of Middle Eastern Studies* 48, no. 4 (August 8, 2021): 596–610.

crisis, I posit that it was not in spite of but due to the Palestine Liberation Organization's identity as an anti-Western revolutionary group—alongside its preexisting ties to the Iranian opposition movement—that the PLO was uniquely positioned to negotiate US interests in post-revolutionary Iran. Political relationships between governments and non-state armed groups are not ideologically fixed; rather, they evolve to reflect the shifting tactical benefits of unexpected but nevertheless opportune alliances.

20th century US-Iran relations

Pre-revolutionary Iran

Arguably few states have undergone a more volatile course of relations throughout the past century than Iran and the United States. Within a broader Cold War context, Western strategic interests were severely undermined by the ambitions of Iran's democratically elected ruler, Mohammad Mossadegh, to eliminate foreign interference from Iranian political affairs and nationalize Iran's oil industry. The country's ample oil reserves and geopolitical proximity to the Soviet Union made it an irreplaceable node in the US global security order. Accordingly, in 1953, Mossadegh was ousted through an Anglo-American engineered coup. The Eisenhower administration promptly reinstated the Pahlavi monarchy, which operated as a uniquely close US ally under Mohammad Reza Shah.

By Nixon's inauguration in January 1969, Iran had become "America's single-largest arms purchaser."³ Under his administration's "twin pillar" approach to off-shore balancing, the US signed a deal that allowed the Shah to "purchase any U.S. weapons system he desired, in any quantity, short of nuclear weapons."⁴ Despite Carter's pro-arms control platform, this blank cheque policy continued under the next two American presidential administrations. However, between the United States' role in ousting Mossadegh and its near-unconditional support for the Iranian monarchy, anti-US sentiments became increasingly widespread in Iran throughout the mid-20th century. The opulence, brutality, and forced secularity of the Shah's regime alienated a majority of the Iranian population, who perceived the monarch as nothing more than an American puppet, predicated upon the might of US petrodollars and a CIA-trained secret police force rather than popular legitimacy.

Revolutionary Iran

By January 1978, nationwide grievances reached a tipping point. Over the next year, Iran erupted into a popular uprising that few predicted: an entire population took to the streets, united under the banner of Islam, to demand the fall of a two-millennia old monarchy backed by the full support of the US military. On January 16, 1979, the Shah fled Iran, signifying that Ayatollah Khomeini and his clerical opposition movement had succeeded in capturing Iranian state power. Critically, the Iranian Revolution marked a significant departure in the trajectory of US-Iranian relations. The Carter administration was now faced with a conservative clerical regime that was

³ Cody Morgan, "U.S. - Iran Relations: A History of Covert Action and a Promising Future" 2 (2015).

⁴ Stephen McGlinchey, "Richard Nixon's Road to Tehran: The Making of the U.S.–Iran Arms Agreement of May 1972," *Diplomatic History* 37, no. 4 (2013): 841–60.

not only ideologically misaligned with the US but directly empowered through anti-American fervour. For the purposes of this paper, US-Iran relations during the immediate post-Revolutionary era can be distinguished by two periods: first, the Provisional Revolutionary Government from February 4, 1979, to November 6, 1979; and second, the Khomeinist elements' consolidation of state power by the Council of the Islamic Revolution from November 6, 1979 onward.⁵

Between February and November 1979, the Carter administration "attempted to develop a working relationship" with the interim Iranian government.⁶ Mehdi Bazargan, the pro-democracy Liberation Movement's leader who had been appointed as first prime minister of post-revolutionary Iran by Khomeini, was thought to be amenable to a "resumption of bilateral cooperation."⁷ According to William Sullivan, the last US ambassador to Iran, Bazargan "advocated a good relation with the West to balance off the Soviet Union," which he—like most Iranian nationalists—did not trust.⁸ However, recognizing Bazargan would likely be replaced by more radical elements in the Revolutionary Council, American officials "tried to avoid actions that would undermine his government or further destabilize Iran."⁹

Presciently, the course of US-Iran relations was altered once again by the seizure of the US embassy in Tehran on November 4th, 1979. Just two days later, Bazargan and his entire cabinet resigned in protest against both the emergent hostage scenario and the clerics' increasing encroachment into politics, extinguishing hopes for moderate democratic governance in post-revolutionary Iran. Following Bazargan's resignation, the Revolutionary Council fully entrenched its rule, establishing the Iranian theocratic republic system that is still in place today. The disintegration of Iran's interim government as a direct result of the embassy seizure exemplifies how the hostage crisis not only shifted the trajectory of American politics but also indirectly drove the further radicalization of the Iranian domestic political sphere.

The Palestine Liberation Organization

Origins

Rather than a comprehensive account of the PLO's development, this section highlights how Arafat's actions during the Iran hostage crisis reflected the organization's evolving strategic and political identity. The Palestine Liberation Organization was founded in May 1964 with the aim of uniting the various factions of the Palestinian nationalist movement under a single umbrella organization. Egypt and Jordan's defeat by Israel in the Six-Day War of 1967 as well as the Palestinian *fedayeen's* mythologized stand against Israel at the Battle of Karamah in 1968 catapulted Fatah, a secular social democratic group, and other armed factions of the Palestinian nationalist movement

⁵ Mohsen M. Milani, *The Making of Iran's Islamic Revolution: From Monarchy to Islamic Republic*, 2nd ed. (Boca Raton, FL: Routledge, 2018).

⁶ Gary Sick, "The Carter Administration," *The Iran Primer* (United States Institute of Peace, October 5, 2000).

⁷ Mark Gasiorowski, "US Covert Operations toward Iran, February–November 1979: Was the CIA Trying to Overthrow the Islamic Regime?," *Middle Eastern Studies* 51, no. 1 (January 2, 2015): 115–35.

⁸ Eva Patricia Raket, "The Iranian Political Elite, State and Society Relations, and Foreign Relations since the Islamic Revolution" (PhD, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research (AISSR), 2008), 151.

⁹ *Ibid.*

into a dominant position within the PLO. In February 1969, at the fifth session of the Palestine National Council, the Palestinian political establishment voiced its support for guerrilla warfare against Israel by appointing Yasser Arafat, one of Fatah's founding members, as president of the PLO.¹⁰ During its first decade, the PLO pursued a particularly militaristic strategy of armed struggle, identified by the organization's 1968 charter as "the only way to liberate Palestine."¹¹ Driven by the guerrilla activity of factions such as the Black September Organization (BSO) and the Popular Front for the Liberation of Palestine (PFLP), the PLO gained the reputation of a group willing to support, if not directly perpetrate, violence against Western civilians.

However, the strategic objectives of the mainstream PLO underwent a seismic internal shift throughout the 1970s. Despite initially escalating its use of regional and international terror, The PLO's defeat at Black September in 1970 and forced relocation from Jordan to Lebanon the following year represented a fundamental failure for the guerilla movement.¹² In subsequent years, however, Arafat became "increasingly aware of the costs" of indiscriminate violence, which not only undermined public opinion of the movement but provoked heavy military reprisals from Israel.¹³ For Sayigh, the spectacle of the Munich massacre at the 1972 Olympics "marked the turning point for the Palestinian leadership" by threatening any diplomatic progress the PLO had made:¹⁴ following that event, Arafat realized that such blatant demonstrations of violence only stifled international sympathy for the Palestinian cause.

The October War of 1973 also set a "new phase of political compromise" in motion across the region as Arab leaders came to recognize the centrality of the Palestinian question in Arab-Israeli hostilities.¹⁵ That year, Arafat came to the conclusion that attacking American and European targets was "counterproductive" to the goals of Palestinian nationalism.¹⁶ On the whole, these developments culminated in June 1974 with the introduction of the PLO's Ten Point Program, a novel vision that Palestinian liberation could be achieved through a "nonmilitary option."¹⁷ This was a considerably more moderate aim than the PLO's early predilection for armed struggle;¹⁸ as Neff provides, the "concept of armed struggle became subservient to political diplomacy" within the PLO's mainstream apparatus from 1974 onward. Nevertheless, Arafat's moderate turn was not embraced by all elements of the PLO: to the contrary, throughout the 1970s, he remained under immense pressure by the

¹⁰ S. Shamir Hassan, "Al-Fatah: A Study of Ideological Evolution," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 61, pt. 2 (2000–2001): 1136–1141.

¹¹ Palestine Liberation Organization, "The Palestinian National Charter: Resolutions of the Palestine National Council July 1-17, 1968," July 1968, p. 112.

¹² Sayigh, *Armed Struggle and the Search for State*.

¹³ *Ibid.*, p. 309.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 310.

¹⁵ Hussam Mohamad, "PLO Strategy: From Total Liberation to Coexistence By Hussam Mohamad," *Palestine-Israel Journal of Politics, Economics, and Culture* 4, no. 2 (1997).

¹⁶ Bird, *The Good Spy*, p. 147.

¹⁷ Manuel Hassassian, "The Democratization Process in the PLO: Ideology, Structure, and Strategy," in *Democracy, Peace, and the Israeli-Palestinian Conflict*, ed. Edy Kaufman, Abed B. Shukri, and Robert L. Rothstein (Boulder, Colorado: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 1993), 257–81, p. 273.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

organization's more radical factions and even by the leftists of his own party, Fatah.¹⁹ In the fall of 1978, all of the groups within the PLO excluding Fatah formed a coalition with Syria and Iraq for the purpose of balancing against Arafat and the mainstream PLO leadership. The head of the PFLP, George Habash, proclaimed during this period that "the time has come to conduct a serious battle with the aim of correcting conditions in the PLO... The battle now is the Palestinian Right."²⁰ Within the organization's more hardline elements, Arafat's incipient acknowledgement that Palestinian nationalists would likely have to settle for sovereignty within only the post-1967 boundaries—Jerusalem, Gaza, and the West Bank, as opposed to the entirety of Historic Palestine—was no different than relinquishing the cause of Palestinian liberation altogether.

PLO-US relations

Public

For the majority of the 20th century, no formal relations existed between the United States and the Palestinian political leadership. Beginning as early as 1947, the State Department abandoned its prior policy of acknowledging "Palestinians' rights as a major community, including the right of self-determination."²¹ This shift, in essence, drove forty-five years of US neglect for the Palestinian question altogether. For Staniland, armed groups' relations to governments can be classified as ideologically opposed, aligned, or "in the grey zone."²² The PLO represents a textbook opposed group: prior to, and arguably after, the Oslo Accords, the Palestinian movement "fundamentally challenged [US] regime ideology," made seemingly "unacceptable political demands that cannot be easily managed within mainstream politics," and professed goals which would "undermine key principles of the regime and nation while encouraging other similar challenges" if the US acknowledged their legitimacy.²³

By the late 1960s and early 1970s, even as the UN General Assembly passed a number of resolutions to begin "establishing the legal and moral framework for Palestinian nationalism," the US (and Israel) opposed each motion.²⁴ Although Henry Kissinger launched a "vigorous new policy of step-by-step diplomacy" with Arab leaders after the "shock" of the October War of 1973, no formal dialogue was pursued with the Palestinians under the Nixon or Ford administrations. To the contrary, Arafat was excluded from two peace processes that significantly impacted other states' policies towards Palestine: the Sinai Interim Agreement (or "Sinai II") between Israel and Egypt in September 1975, and the Camp David Accords of March 1979.

The Sinai Interim Agreement, an archetypal example of Henry Kissinger's "shuttle diplomacy," severely impaired the United States' prospect of developing a

¹⁹ Sayigh, *Armed Struggle and the Search for State*, p. 432-434.

²⁰ Sayigh, *Armed Struggle and the Search for State*, p. 443.

²¹ Donald Neff, *Fallen Pillars: U.S. Policy Towards Palestine and Israel since 1945* (Washington, D.C.: Institute of Palestine Studies, 1995).

²² Paul Staniland, *Ordering Violence: Explaining Armed Group-State Relations from Conflict to Cooperation* (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2021).

²³ *Ibid.*

²⁴ *Ibid.*

working security partnership with the PLO in the mid-to-late twentieth century. Needing to appease Israel into accepting the terms of a peaceful territorial settlement with Egypt, Kissinger secretly pledged during the Sinai II talks that the US would “not recognize or negotiate with the Palestine Liberation Organization so long as the [PLO] does not recognize Israel’s right to exist or accept Security Council Resolutions 242 and 33.”²⁵ Kissinger’s pledge set the normative precedent that no US officials could make direct contact with the PLO, significantly restricting the extent to which the United States could diplomatically engage with Palestinians for the subsequent decades. Consequently, as evidenced by this article’s later sections, the US could not directly contact the PLO throughout the entire Iran hostage crisis; instead, interlocutors were utilized for all US-PLO communications. True to word, the policy remained in place until 1988, when Arafat capitulated by recognizing Israel’s right to exist and fully denouncing violence as a Palestinian liberational imperative.

However, as Jensehaugen highlights, Kissinger’s pledge was interpreted differently by each subsequent administration. Upon entering office, increased concerns about alienating the Israeli lobby in D.C. drove Carter away from engaging with the Palestinians. In fact, the President acceded to the custom of Kissinger’s pledge to not speak with the PLO to a more extreme degree than Ford, his predecessor, despite initial signs that Carter would be more amenable to the Palestinian plight.²⁶ According to a February 8, 1977 memo from the acting CIA director to Zbigniew Brzezinski (Carter’s National Security Advisor), Carter turned down an offer from Arafat to “[open] a dialogue with the US government” early in his presidency. To stem any criticism of antisemitism, Carter exercised little creativity in attempting to find an opening toward dialogue with the Palestinian—until the Iran hostage crisis necessitated such contact.

As follows, the Camp David Accords further altered the trajectory of US-PLO relations. Despite the fact that the status of Palestine was a critical issue addressed in the Accords, Palestinians were completely sidelined from the Egyptian-Israeli peace talks in March 1979. This exclusion only further incensed hardline factions of the PLO against Arafat, whose stature was already under threat from the growing authority of the militant PFLP. By snubbing the Palestinian cause, Camp David only further undermined the moderate factions of the Palestinian nationalist movement, confirming hardliner convictions that Palestinian liberation could only be achieved through armed struggle. By rebuffing Arafat’s attempts to garner international legitimacy through diplomacy, US policymakers made his moderate position appear increasingly weak and strategically isolated within the broader Palestinian resistance movement.

Private

A stark contrast emerged during the late twentieth century between the United States’ public stance towards the PLO and its select covert engagement with

²⁵ Edward R.F. Sheehan, “How Kissinger Did It: Step by Step in the Middle East,” *Foreign Policy* 22, no. Spring 1976 (Spring 1976): 3–70, p. 63.

²⁶ Neff, *Fallen Pillars: U.S. Policy Towards Palestine and Israel since 1945*, p. 117.

Palestinian political leaders throughout the Levant. In 1969, Robert Ames, the chief of the Near East and South Asia Division of the CIA's Directorate of Intelligence, reportedly established a back-channel line of communication with a high-ranking member of the PLO, Ali Hassan Salameh. Salameh, or Abu Hassan as he was known, was Fatah's security chief as well as one of the leaders of the militant Black September Movement. Owing to Ames, the CIA maintained an indirect channel of communication with the PLO in Beirut throughout the 1970s.²⁷

Palestinian contacts permitted American operatives a degree of manoeuvrability in 1970s Lebanon that would have otherwise been impossible. By the end of the decade, use of the channel had expanded beyond intelligence operatives. After arriving in Lebanon in 1978, John Gunther Dean, the US Ambassador to Lebanon, was also authorized to coordinate activity with the PLO in the interest of "security matters and in defence of American interests."²⁸ Contrary to conventional wisdom, the Ambassador insists that the PLO was not behind the assassination of Ambassador Frank Meloy in Beirut in 1976, but, rather, helped the US locate and retrieve his body.²⁹ Harold H. Saunders, the Assistant Secretary of State between 1978 and 1991, also corroborated Dean's general account of US-PLO collusion in 1970s Beirut. Several years after leaving office, Saunders professed that the PLO not only "provided security in much of the area around the American Embassy in Beirut but 'guaranteed security when Americans were evacuated in 1976 after the Lebanese civil war broke out.'"³⁰ In fact, according to Jensehaugen, the Carter administration later publicly justified its contacts with Arafat during the hostage crisis by "citing [...] the Beirut evacuation."³¹ Moreover, in the context of this article, Saunders and Dean's testimonies exemplify the PLO's precedent of assisting the US during moments of crisis. As such, situational US-PLO collaboration in the Middle East from the mid-1970s onward represents, as argued in this paper, a "rare" order of limited cooperation between an opposed group and government with shared tactical interests.³²

PLO-Iran relations

Before the hostage crisis, the PLO maintained a sturdy ideological and security alliance with Iran's clerical regime. The Palestinians' association with the Islamic Republic can be traced back to the mid-1960s, when Iranian Marxist organizations participated in PLO guerrilla training camps in Jordan and South Yemen.³³ The relationship between Palestinian militants and the Khomeinist elements of the Iranian revolution then deepened throughout the 1970s in Lebanon, where the ongoing civil war and general state of governmental disarray provided a "training ground for

²⁷ Ames was eventually killed in the 1984 US Embassy bombing in Beirut.

²⁸ John Gunther Dean, Ambassador John Gunther Dean, interview by Charles Stuart Kennedy, *Association for Diplomatic Studies and Training*, September 6, 2000, p. 133.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Harold H. Saunders, "Diplomacy and Pressure," in *American Hostages in Iran* (New Haven and London: Yale University Press, 1985).

³¹ Jensehaugen, "A Palestinian Window of Opportunity?," p. 600.

³² Staniland, *Ordering Violence*.

³³ Tony Badran, "Iranian Revolution: Arafat and the Ayatollahs," *Tablet Magazine*, January 17, 2019.

revolutionaries from all over the world.”³⁴ Considering Moghadam’s “typology of terrorist inter-group cooperation,” the ideological, logistical, and strategic alliance between the PLO guerrilla movement and pre-Revolutionary Iranian militants represented a high level of cooperation between non-state armed groups.³⁵ After the triumph of the Iranian Revolution in February 1979, Arafat became the first “foreign leader” invited to Tehran, where he and fifty-eight other PLO delegates were ceremonially welcomed and handed the key to the former Israeli Embassy.³⁶ During that visit, however, a meeting held between Arafat and Khomeini evidently soured. The Ayatollah reportedly encouraged Arafat to “model the PLO on the principles of the Islamic revolution”—which was antithetical to the secular model of governance advocated by Fatah—and criticized the Palestinian organization’s “nationalist and pan-Arab agenda.”³⁷ As I will later examine in greater detail, the Iranian revolutionaries’ ascent to state power—thereby transforming from a carrier movement to a government, per Staniland³⁸—shifted the power balance between Khomeini and Arafat in a manner which undermined the PLO’s manoeuvrability during the Iran hostage crisis.

PLO involvement in hostage negotiations

Having detailed the pre-existing relations between the US, the PLO, and Iran, we can now turn to the primary focus of this article: the Iran hostage crisis itself. At the time of the crisis, the PLO’s participation in early hostage negotiations was relatively well detailed in the mainstream news. However, over the past four decades, Palestinian efforts to resolve the crisis on behalf of the Carter administration have been expunged from the historical record. This section analyses the PLO’s purported involvement in two episodes during the hostage crisis: first, the Iranian regime’s initial release of thirteen American hostages in late November 1979; and second, its decision to return the bodies of eight US servicemen killed in Iran during Operation Eagle Claw in early May 1980.

Start of crisis: November 1979 - January 1980

On November 4, 1979, Iranian students seized the US Embassy in Tehran and took sixty-six American embassy workers hostage. In the first several days after the embassy’s capture, an American special crisis task force headed by Saunders dubbed the Iran Working Group began reaching out to any individual, organization, or government around the world that “might have influence with revolutionary leadership in Iran.”³⁹ Across primary accounts, a disagreement emerges over whether it was the US or the PLO who first initiated contact over the hostage crisis. On one hand, Gary

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Assaf Moghadam, “Terrorist Affiliations in Context: A Typology of Terrorist Inter-Group Cooperation,” *CTC Sentinel*, Combating Terrorism Center, U.S. Military Academy, March 2015.

³⁶ Rachel Brandenburg, “Iran and the Palestinians,” *The Iran Primer* (United States Institute of Peace, October 13, 2010).

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Staniland, *Ordering Violence*.

³⁹ Harold H. Saunders, “The Crisis Begins,” in *American Hostages in Iran* (New Haven and London: Yale University Press, 1985), p. 68.

Sick, a member of the National Security Council Staff for the Middle East/North Africa who was involved in top-secret conversations throughout the crisis, contended that the PLO first contacted the White House. In contrast, all other reputable accounts of the development—including President Carter’s own diary—indicate that the US instigated contact with the Palestinians. The latter perspective is also supported by a CIA Intelligence Information Cable from November 7th, 1979 that discloses Arafat was contacted by a member of the Carter administration within two days of the inception of the crisis. Considering this overwhelming evidence alongside Saunders’ description of the Working Group’s mass outreach effort to open “as many channels of communication as possible” in the early stage of the crisis, we can likely conclude that the US did in fact reach out to the PLO first in November 1979.

Neither the State Department nor CIA have declassified the name of the government official who first initiated contact with the PLO. However, Ambassador Dean revealed decades later that Washington asked him to gauge “whether the Palestinians might be able to help to obtain the release of the American hostages.”⁴⁰ Evidently, by this point, former Attorney General Ramsey Clark, one of two civilian “special emissaries” during the crisis, was also in touch with a number of Palestinian contacts in the US and Lebanon.⁴¹ Dean recalls how he reached out to several Palestinians, including Brigadier Sa’d al-Sayil—one of the military leaders of Fatah, henceforth referred to by his nom de guerre, “Abu Walid”—to inquire whether they could “do anything to get our hostages in Tehran liberated.”⁴² Consequently, to the relief of high-ranking US government officials, Arafat dispatched a Palestinian mission to Tehran on November 6th “for the purpose of freeing American embassy personnel currently being held as prisoners in the Embassy.”⁴³ The Palestinian convoy consisted of Abu Walid and two other high-ranking Fatah officials: Hani al-Hasan, Arafat’s political advisor and Tehrani envoy, and Khalil al-Wazir, Fatah’s military chief (henceforth referred to as “Abu Jihad”).⁴⁴ Arafat’s representatives landed in Tehran sometime between the 7th and 8th of November, 1979, where their presence over the next week or so was quite widely reported by American newspapers.

The PLO’s swift response to the Iran hostage crisis raises a crucial question: why was Arafat so committed to resolving America’s hostage problem? Through the simplified prism of Cold War bipolarity, the Palestinians’ effort to negotiate on behalf of the US appears contradictory. As noted, Arafat’s proximity to the clerical regime went far beyond “ideological solidarity,” to employ Walt’s terminology:⁴⁵ in May 1979, his own operatives helped establish the Iranian Revolutionary Guard.⁴⁶ Unlike the PLO’s

⁴⁰ Gunther Dean, Ambassador John Gunther Dean, p. 140.

⁴¹ Harold H. Saunders, “Diplomacy and Pressure,” p. 77.

⁴² *Ibid.*, p. 141.

⁴³ *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 32; Foreign Relations of the United States, 1977-1980. “Iran: Hostage Crisis, November 1979-September 1980.” Volume XI, Part I, Document No. 16, p. 38. Edited by Linda Qaimmaqami and Kathleen B. Rasmussen. United States Government Publishing Office. Washington, D.C., 2020 (hereafter referred to as FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document number, page number).

⁴⁵ Stephen M. Walt, *The Origins of Alliances* (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1987).

⁴⁶ Badran, “Iranian Revolution.”

efforts to retrieve Frank Meloy's body from Beirut three years prior, the hostage crisis in Iran bore no impact on Palestinian affairs, nor did the PLO have an extensive network in place on the ground in Iran it could easily activate. Despite these hurdles, however, the PLO embarked on a determined mission to resolve the Iran hostage crisis. In fact, Palestinian leaders emphasized in their communications with the US that "the PLO sought no quid pro quo [...] in return for their efforts" during the Iran crisis and hoped for nothing more than "some kind of private acknowledgement of what they were doing."⁴⁷ Khalid al-Hassan, a senior Fatah advisor and representative in Tehran, even requested that the "PLO [...] not to be thanked for anything it achieves in this situation" because "hatred of the U.S. in Iran is so great."⁴⁸

Despite the PLO's purported desire for secrecy, we can analyse the PLO's keen involvement in the Iran hostage crisis as reflective of Arafat's pursuit of political legitimacy within the international community. As the 1970s progressed, Arafat had tired of other Arab leaders' attempts to influence the PLO. This is reflected by a September 1976 memorandum, when then-CIA director George Bush informs Kissinger that "the mood within the PLO leadership is definitely one of trying to [...] resist exploitation by other Arab states for their own purposes." Bush also assessed that "disillusionment" with local relations made the PLO "far more ready to compromise than it was in the past."⁴⁹ Yet, hopes that the Carter administration would be more amenable to engaging with the Palestinians than his predecessors were quickly dashed after the president declined Arafat's appeal for dialogue with the US government in February 1977. After this disappointment, Arafat resorted to improving PLO relations with the USSR, an endeavour which, nevertheless, was designed to "impress the US with the centrality of the PLO in Middle East politics."⁵⁰

The inception of the hostage crisis thus presented Arafat with an unexpected opportunity to curry goodwill with the United States, demonstrate his own diplomatic prowess, and minimize the PLO's dependence on the other Arab leaders. Although Arafat's interest in formally engaging with the US was not novel, the hostage crisis quickly precipitated a shift in the "tactical incentives" that the US had to gain by working with the PLO.⁵¹ On November 7th, 1979, the Austrian Chancellor, Bruno Kreisky, evidently advanced a plan for the Carter administration to "take a 'demonstrable action' openly and directly with the PLO" and "request publicly that Arafat and the PLO help obtain the hostages' freedom," a move equivalent to de-facto recognition of the PLO. Sources differ over whether it was the US or Israel who halted the progress of a public PLO channel by this point, but nevertheless, the plan did not come to fruition. Kissinger's 1975 pledge against directly contacting the PLO was cited in internal communications as a determining factor in Carter's decision to forego this early proposal for resolving the hostage crisis. Although nothing came of the plan, its details provide an intriguing lens into how different members of the Carter

⁴⁷ Saunders, "Diplomacy and Pressure," p. 78.

⁴⁸ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 29, p. 64.

⁴⁹ FRUS, 1969-1976, Volume XXVI, Arab-Israeli Dispute, 1974-1976, Document 293.

⁵⁰ Yezid Sayigh, *Armed Struggle and the Search for State: The Palestinian National Movement, 1949-1993* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1998), p. 426.

⁵¹ Staniland, *Ordering Violence*.

administration approached the matter of crisis management as well as how this situation of governmental desperation almost drove the US to adopt a measure it, for so long, considered antithetical to its domestic and regional interests in the Middle East.

The Ayatollah's "affirmative action"

As soon as the PLO mission arrived in Iran, Ramsey Clark immediately requested that the Carter administration "forego any official approach to the UN for the time being" in the interest of fully testing the PLO channel.⁵² Communications between members of the Working Group and other US cabinet members show that ensuring the PLO's ability to act unobstructed on the ground in Tehran was a clear priority. The US quickly came to the recognition that "any proposal put to [Khomeini] should appeal to his own positions and beliefs. Offers to bargain, mediate or negotiate will not work."⁵³ That is precisely why high-ranking members of the Carter administration promptly assessed that "the PLO's stance of not speaking for the US is a very sound one" for resolving the hostage situation. Thus, in a briefing conducted on November 8th, the Director of the Office for Combating Terrorism stipulated that the PLO's efforts in Iran should "go forward without any direct link or association to the US," and that the organization's "known antagonism to the US is a very positive aspect in dealing with Khomeini."⁵⁴

Between November 19th and 20th, 1979, the Iranian students released thirteen embassy hostages who were all either women or Black men.⁵⁵ Justifying the release, the Ayatollah declared that "Islam reserves special rights for women" and that "[Black people] for a long time have lived under oppression and pressure in America and may have been sent [to Iran under duress]."⁵⁶ According to Sanders, this release was not negotiated but "an Iranian gesture unilaterally taken. Whether they made their decision at PLO urging or because they recognized the need to improve their position, we were never sure."⁵⁷ However, by closely examining declassified Carter administration documents and news reports from the first weeks of the crisis, a clear trail of PLO involvement emerges. Though Jensehaugen proposes that the initial hostage release "so shortly after the PLO mission had gone to Iran does not seem coincidental," I go a step further and argue that, based on the aforementioned primary evidence, the PLO was irrefutably responsible for securing these hostages' release.⁵⁸

Between public media and private correspondences, two distinct narratives emerge of what happened after the Palestinian mission arrived in Tehran. First, as noted, the activity of the PLO mission was well documented by American newspapers during its first week in Iran. Nevertheless, public optimism surrounding Arafat's chance to liberate the hostages quickly waned. Reports began emerging from Tehran that Khomeini had refused to meet with Abu Walid, and the Iranian students would not

⁵² FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 13, p. 32.

⁵³ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 16, p. 38.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Two women and one Black man were not released.

⁵⁶ Jonathan C. R. and al, "Women, Blacks Ordered Freed in Iran," *Washington Post*, November 18, 1979.

⁵⁷ Saunders, "Diplomacy and Pressure," p. 79.

⁵⁸ Jensehaugen, "A Palestinian Window of Opportunity?" p. 606.

accept negotiations, “whether by the PLO, [its chairman] Yasser Arafat, or by anyone else.”⁵⁹ At this time, Abu Walid and other Palestinian figures in Iran appear to rebuke all suggestions that the PLO was interested in the hostages’ release, leading to the overall impression that Arafat was not, in fact, concerned with the crisis.

While it is true that the Palestinians were met with greater resistance in Iran than anticipated, Arafat was keenly aware of how the PLO’s presence in Iran might be perceived by different parties. A secret CIA memo from later that month corroborates that “the Palestinians made some serious miscalculations in their initial efforts to obtain the release of the hostages,” leading to “cool treatment” by the Revolutionary Council.⁶⁰ However, the document also reveals insights into an intentional joint effort to conceal all traces of collaboration between the US and the PLO throughout the remainder of the hostage crisis. With the consent of the Carter administration, the PLO projected decisively anti-American sentiments to “protect its flanks,” so to speak, and “ensure Fatah’s continued access to Iranian officials.”⁶¹ Arafat and his colleagues attempted to distance themselves from the US, denying any “mediation role” and stressing Palestinian support for Khomeini through various public statements.⁶²

Given this knowledge, a second narrative of PLO involvement in hostage negotiations starts to materialize. On November 13th, 1979, the PLO envoy to Tehran, Hani al-Hasan, met with Khomeini for several hours. During this meeting, a committee consisting of Khomeini, al-Hassan, and representatives from both the Iranian Foreign Ministry and the student hostage takers was established to “arrange that the ‘[Black people], women, and children’ be released to the PLO.”⁶³ The next day, Ambassador Dean confirmed that he had received a letter from the PLO affirming that Iran would release hostages from these minority groups by November 16th. Although that initial release date was not met—reportedly due to complications with the Iranian students—by November 17th, the deal was back on: Khomeini publicized the development and publicly announced that all Black or female hostages “not guilty of espionage” would be released. During a Special Coordination Committee Meeting in Washington that same day, a plan for the hostages’ release was laid out:

“Arrangements have been made with the Swiss to fly them out when the release actually occurs. They will go to Frankfurt for medical examination and a rest of a day or so before coming back to the U.S. We expect about 10–12 people. We do not know how the transfer will actually take place. The hostages may be released to the PLO or some other intermediary.”⁶⁴

At the same time, Arafat was in Riyadh, where, at the behest of the US, he was pressed “to continue the PLO effort with the Iranians” by the Saudi Foreign Minister.⁶⁵ Playing

⁵⁹ Jonathan C. R and al, “Iranians Reject PLO Mediation on Hostages,” *Washington Post*, November 9, 1979.

⁶⁰ Central Intelligence Agency, “Palestinian Involvement in US-Iran Dispute,” November 21, 1979.

⁶¹ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 29, p. 64.

⁶² *Ibid.*

⁶³ *Ibid.*

⁶⁴ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 35, p. 77.

⁶⁵ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 43, p. 108.

into the Fatah leader's own interests, the Saudis reportedly emphasized to Arafat how the "PLO image in the United States and the world at large" would be "immeasurably enhanced if it can somewhat succeed in getting the hostages released."⁶⁶

And "somewhat succeed" they did. A first batch of three hostages—two Black marines and one female secretary—was released early on November 19th and promptly transported to Wiesbaden, West Germany. That night, within the US Embassy courtyard, the hostage takers staged a press conference. Reportedly, "several hundred foreign and local reporters were let into the embassy" to interview the additional ten hostages who were to be released the next day.⁶⁷ Finally, on the morning of November 20th, the second batch of ten hostages was liberated; exiting the Embassy at 6:55 am, they immediately departed Tehran on Iran Air flight 775 to Paris.⁶⁸ With that, thirteen of the sixty-six embassy hostages were free.

The PLO's role in these thirteen hostages' release is thoroughly substantiated by Carter administration documents. In a December 13, 1979 telegram to the State Department and White House, Secretary Vance goes as far as stating that Arafat had been "very helpful in gaining the release of the first thirteen hostages."⁶⁹ Knowledge of this episode of successful US-PLO cooperation also appeared to have piqued the interest of foreign leaders. Upon visiting the White House on December 17th, Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher remarked to Carter that "the U.S. public did not know how helpful the PLO had been during the Iran crisis."⁷⁰ Palestinian influence may also help explain the fact that hostages specifically from minority groups were released in late November. The PLO appears to have been the first party to suggest releasing Black hostages "in recognition of [the group's] own rapprochement" with the American Civil Rights Movement and Black Panther Party. According to a PLO representative in Tehran, the Palestinians suggested liberating the Black hostages as a gesture honouring "Andrew Young's resignation as U.S. ambassador to the United Nations" the previous summer.⁷¹

After this noteworthy opening, the PLO remained quite active in negotiation efforts for two months. In fact, shortly after the thirteen hostages' release, Secretary Vance identified the PLO as one of the National Security Council's two "main channels" in Iran alongside the UN. Throughout the first weeks of December, American or Saudi personnel were in near daily contact with Arafat, working to persuade the Chairman to go to Iran and bargain with the Ayatollah. However, by this point, Arafat began acting with heightened caution. In several internal memoranda from December 1979 through late January 1980, various members of Carter's cabinet expressed the opinion that although Arafat was eager to solve the hostage crisis himself, he was waiting to visit Tehran until it was clear his actions would "result in something substantial."⁷² Given

⁶⁶ Ibid.

⁶⁷ Kifner, "Iranians Who Seized U.S. Embassy Release 4 Women and 6 Black Men," *The New York Times*, November 20, 1979, sec. Archives.

⁶⁸ Ibid.

⁶⁹ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 95, p. 248.

⁷⁰ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 103, p. 279.

⁷¹ Jonathan C. R. and al, "Women, Blacks Ordered Freed in Iran".

⁷² FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 143, p. 375.

Arafat's gamble to work with the US, the possibility that his actions would not pay off risked not only harming his alliance with Khomeini, but incentivizing further backlash against his leadership in the PLO. As Jensehaugen highlights, collaborating with the US so soon after Camp David would not have been well-received by the more hardline factions of the Palestinian resistance. This reflects the CIA's earlier assessment in late November that Arafat had a precedent of "discreetly support[ing] actions that were at the same time being criticized by PLO spokesmen." However, Arafat recognized how his actions could impact the delicate balance of power across the various factions of the PLO, issuing what the CIA viewed as "anti-imperialist pronouncements [...] designed in part to maintain his own revolutionary credentials."⁷³ This statement exemplifies the pressure Arafat was under to appeal to the interests of three disparate audiences: the US, the PLO, and the Ayatollah.

Middle of crisis: February - May 1980

However, by February 1980, mentions of Arafat or the PLO in Carter administration documents pertaining to the hostage situation cease altogether. Throughout these middle months of the crisis, the PLO's influence in Iran appears to have diminished significantly. Given the lack of information, we cannot be certain as to the reason why this occurs. However, the disintegration of Iran's interim government posed an unexpected challenge for the Palestinians who had flown to Tehran anticipating negotiations with Bazargan, only to discover upon landing that his government no longer existed. Seemingly, the PLO's leverage with the Ayatollah only waned as months passed and the hardline factions of the clerical regime further entrenched their influence over the Iranian political sphere.

By mid-April 1980, efforts by the US and its allies to negotiate an end to the hostage crisis had reached an impasse. No additional hostages had been released since the initial thirteen in November 1979. Moreover, with the 1980 US Presidential Election quickly approaching that upcoming November, the domestic political ramifications of the crisis were becoming costlier by the day. Coupled with mounting concerns from within the Carter administration that US credibility in Iran would increasingly wane so long as they delayed utilizing force, on April 10th, the President reached a conclusion: America could "no longer afford to depend on diplomacy."⁷⁴ Accordingly, the next day, the National Security Council decided to move forward with a plan to militarily rescue the hostages from Tehran. After five and a half months of preparation, the mission, codenamed "Operation Eagle Claw," was set for April 24th, 1980.

Operation Eagle Claw

The plan was as follows: on the night of the 24th, three MC-180 aircrafts would transport roughly 130 troops more than a thousand miles from Masirah, an island off the coast of Oman, to Desert One, a secure US staging base in Iran's South Khorasan province. Eight helicopters from the USS Nimitz, an aircraft carrier six hundred miles away in the Gulf of Oman, would fly to Desert One, refuel, then transport

⁷³ Central Intelligence Agency, "Palestinian Involvement in US-Iran Dispute".

⁷⁴ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 250, p. 677.

most of the special operation forces to a second base outside of Tehran, Desert Two.⁷⁵ The troops were to hide at Desert Two the next day; then, on the night of the 25th, two CIA agents already positioned inside Iran would drive the assault team into Tehran. The ground forces would split up, extricate the hostages from two locations, and evacuate all personnel.⁷⁶

The mission ended in colossal failure. Under-equipped due to technical failures and behind schedule, a helicopter and C-130 collided at Desert One while both attempting to refuel, killing eight crew members. Low on fuel and desperate to flee the scene, the remaining aircrafts were forced to leave the deceased commandos' bodies behind. This operational disaster left President Carter with a second crisis to navigate: Iran was now in possession of eight US servicemen's bodies. In the coming days, the Islamic Republic exploited the military blunder as an opportunity to humiliate the US and rally domestic support for itself. The regime is alleged to have publicly displayed the charred remains of the commandos, showed footage of their bodies and the aircraft wreckage at Desert One on national television, and encouraged civilians to "celebrate the abortive rescue mission."⁷⁷

Yet, what could have developed into a months or even years-long battle over custody of the commandos' remains was, unlike the hostage crisis itself, promptly rectified. By April 27th, President Banisadr publicly voiced that "the bodies of the eight members of the rescue team who perished in the mission will be returned to the U.S. 'with no conditions attached.'"⁷⁸ In a State Department SITREP from that same day, "Diplomatic Sources" are cited as having revealed that the eight bodies had been moved to the nearby city of Tabas and would be "handed over to the Swiss Embassy," which was representing the US on the ground in Iran.⁷⁹ This episode of the crisis as well as the particular language of this SITREP, begs two questions: why was Iran willing to release the Americans' bodies so quickly? And who were these "Diplomatic Sources?"

Arafat in action?

Several works of existing literature on the Iran hostage crisis have alluded to the PLO's potential role in securing the release of the bodies of eight US servicemen killed during Operation Eagle Claw. Curiously, Jensehaugen also draws attention to the PLO's potential role in securing the release of the eight commandos' bodies but acknowledges that the claim is difficult to verify given a lack of public information.⁸⁰ His argument draws from two independent yet ultimately unverifiable statements from writer Kai Bird and journalist David Ignatius. First, Bird directly states that Arafat had "helped the Americans retrieve the bodies of their eight servicemen killed at Desert

⁷⁵ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 266, p. 724.

⁷⁶ Edward T. Russel, "Crisis in Iran: OPERATION EAGLE CLAW." *Short of War: Major USAF Contingency Operations 1947-1997*. (Washington, DC: Department of Defense, 2012), p. 129.

⁷⁷ "IRAN SITREP NO. 297." State to ALDEC. April 27, 1980; Phil McCombs and Thomas Morgan, "Corpse Display in Iran Shocks, Enrages Americans," *Washington Post*, April 29, 1980.

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*

⁷⁹ *Ibid.*

⁸⁰ Jensehaugen, "A Palestinian Window of Opportunity?"

One.”⁸¹ Ignatius echoes a similar statement in a 1988 article in the *Washington Post*.⁸² Yet, when Jensehaugen reached out to both writers, attempting to further verify the claim, neither could recall his original source. Until now, this claim has remained unverifiable. The aforementioned SITREPS from April 1980, however, shed light on previously unexamined evidence that the PLO was plausibly responsible for extracting the eight US commandos’ bodies from Iran. Significantly, these documents draw our attention to a PLO-aligned actor who, until now, has gone unacknowledged within the literature.

The arms-dealing Archbishop

One fascinating figure is noticeably absent from most accounts of the multilateral efforts that took place in the spring of 1980 to resolve the hostage crisis: Archbishop Hilarion Capucci. Referred to as the “Father of the Palestinians” and the “Archbishop of the Arabs,” the Syrian-born, Melkite Greek Catholic Archbishop of Jerusalem gained prominence after serving three years in Israeli prison for using his diplomatic status to smuggle arms to Palestinian militants in the West Bank in 1974. The Carter administration first approached Archbishop Capucci on March 29th, 1980 “about traveling to Tehran to meet with the American hostages during Easter week.”⁸³ In addition to providing spiritual comfort, Capucci agreed to the request in order to “explore the possibilities for the release of the hostages.”⁸⁴ In a letter to the State Department from around that period, the Swiss Ambassador to Iran, David Lang, declares the Archbishop to be as possibly “the best person in all the world” for the situation, with the “greatest capacity to persuade because he is ‘not involved.’”⁸⁵

The Archbishop arrived in Tehran on April 5th, 1980; there, he met with Khomeini, the Iranian students, and the hostages, whilst forming a committee composed of Ambassador Lang and others to “find a solution to the crisis.”⁸⁶ After spending several hours with the student hostage takers, Capucci ascertained that the majority of the militants were prepared to end the crisis. His activity is well-documented over the next several days; then, after the 8th, it is unclear how much longer the Archbishop remained in Iran. Capucci enters the picture once more at the end of that month, immediately following the fiasco at Desert One. He returned to Tehran on April 29th, 1980, this time reportedly at the invitation of President Banisadr, to help arrange the transfer of the eight bodies with the Red Cross and the Swiss, then accompany the remains to Europe. While in Iran, he travelled to Tabas, visiting the “morgue where the bodies [were] being kept” and the “site of the commandos’ wrecked aircraft in the desert.”⁸⁷ On May 6th, 1980, Capucci and Ambassador Lang escorted the

⁸¹ Bird, *The Good Spy*, p. 243.

⁸² David Ignatius, “THE SECRET HISTORY OF U.S.-PLO TERROR TALKS,” *Washington Post*, December 4, 1988.

⁸³ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 242, p. 637.

⁸⁴ Department of State, Records of David D. Newsom, Under Secretary of State for Political Affairs, Subject Files, 1978-1981, Lot 81D154, Iran NODIS Cables Mar 1980. Quoted in *Ibid*.

⁸⁵ *Ibid*.

⁸⁶ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 243, p. 639.

⁸⁷ John Kifner, “Prelate Arrives in Iran to Help With Transfer of Bodies,” *The New York Times*, April 30, 1980.

eight bodies from Tehran to Zurich, where they were then transported back to the US by the Red Cross.

Capucci and the Palestinians

Thus, between declassified government documents and personal testimonies from US intelligence personnel, two potential actors emerge in explaining how the commandos' bodies were released from Iran: the Palestine Liberation Organization and Archbishop Capucci. However, I argue that these two actors likely constitute one single channel. Given Capucci's extensive connections with the Palestinian resistance, a close examination of primary documents strongly alludes to the possibility that Capucci was acting in accordance with the PLO to at least some degree in Tehran during the spring of 1980. Capucci's ties to high-ranking members of the PLO such as Suleiman al-Najjab, aka "Abu Firas," and Abu Jihad—one of the three Palestinians Arafat sent to Tehran in November 1979—date back to the mid-1960s. While imprisoned by the Israeli state in the mid-70s, the archbishop periodically exchanged letters with Arafat, who he colloquially addresses as "Brother" and maintained a relationship with the Chairman until the latter's death in the early 2000s.⁸⁸ Capucci was not merely aligned with Palestinian liberation—it was the cause to which his entire life's work was dedicated. Though not a PLO official, the archbishop viewed himself as a voluntary member of the organization's ranks, referring to the PLO as his "family."⁸⁹ Furthermore, due to Capucci's imprisonment, he was strictly prohibited by the Vatican from "any activity related to the Palestinian cause." As a result, the archbishop was unable to publicly collaborate or communicate with the PLO, meaning that any possible contact between Capucci and Arafat during this period would have had to be undertaken in complete secrecy.

Capucci was viewed by the US as an advantageous channel during the crisis specifically because of his close association with the Palestinian liberation movement. In an aforementioned message from Lang to the State Department, the Swiss Ambassador to Iran states:

"Capucci is religious, Palestinian, favourably viewed by the students, well viewed by the Imam, he knows what it is to be a captive, but above all intelligent. He could make the Imam understand that the affair is costing Iran as much as the USA and that it is likely to cost much more."⁹⁰

Additionally, the Archbishop had a potentially useful connection with the student hostage takers: though obviously not Muslim himself, Capucci's liberation theology resonated with the particular rendition of Shi'ism that Revolutionary Iran was purported to have been founded upon, a connection that undoubtedly boded well with the student hostage takers. That Capucci and various PLO representatives were both

⁸⁸ Adel Beshara, trans., *In the Name of God: The Archbishop Who Armed the PLO* (London: Black House Publishing Limited, 2019).

⁸⁹ *Ibid.* p. 40, 127.

⁹⁰ FRUS, 1977-80, Volume XI, Part I, Document 242, p. 637-638.

in Iran in the spring of 1980 is reason enough to surmise that contact was likely made between the Archbishop and Palestinian elements on the ground.

This argument is further strengthened by revelations from Robert Ames' posthumous biography. According to the operatives' principal deputy, Robert Earl, Ames appears to have had a significant role in planning the failed mission at Desert One. "Bitterly disappointed" with the results of this military catastrophe, Ames reportedly worked through his Palestinian contact, Mustafa Zein, to "[arrange] for Arafat to use his contacts in Tehran to obtain the bodies of the eight U.S. servicemen."⁹¹ This evidence is compelling: the Archbishop was a known "contact" of Arafat and was one of two individuals publicly at the centre of the release of the commandos' bodies. Without explicitly stating that Capucci was coordinating with the PLO, this revelation, when considered alongside other hints of liaison between these two actors, verifies with near certainty that Arafat continued exerting influence to resolve the hostage crisis through Archbishop Capucci in the spring of 1980. Given the precedent of the archbishop's fierce Palestinian activism, immense commitment to Palestinian liberation, and close contacts with Palestinian leadership, rejecting the likely possibility that Capucci was in contact with the PLO during his personal involvement in efforts to resolve the Iran hostage crisis would ignore the blatant proximity of his "humanitarian" work with the political aims of the PLO. When evaluated alongside statements indicating that Arafat was responsible for arranging the commandos' bodies release, the odds that the PLO would happen to be brought up in connection to an affair that Capucci was publicly involved in, with no underlying connection, seems like far too much of a coincidence to not bear some resemblance of truth.

Conclusion

Through analysing the PLO's activity throughout the Iran hostage crisis and scrutinizing the possible motives that drove Arafat to covertly align with the US against the Islamic Republic, this article has demonstrated how resolving Cold War-era international crises required temporary tactical alliances across ideological divisions. Because geopolitical autonomy, "neither East, nor West," was one of the underlying driving objectives of the Iranian Revolution, any move that could be perceived as acquiescing to external pressures would ostensibly have been rejected by the student hostage takers. Therefore, due to its outwardly hostile relationship with the US, the PLO was uniquely positioned to advocate for US interests in post-revolutionary Iran. Though Arafat's public image shifted considerably in the post-Oslo era, the PLO was still very much perceived as a terrorist organization by the West in the late 1970s. As a staunch ally of the Islamic Republic and a non-aligned revolutionary movement in its own right, the PLO could reason with the Ayatollah without incurring suspicion. As a Muslim liberation leader, Arafat could also level with Khomeini that releasing the hostages and ending the crisis was in the clerics' own political and strategic interest. That the US bet so heavily on Arafat—going as far as to halt UN activity in Tehran to ensure PLO efforts on the ground could persist unsullied—illustrates how desperate the Carter administration

⁹¹ Bird, *The Good Spy*, p. 239.

was to solve the hostage crisis.

Unfortunately, the mercurial political situation on the ground in Tehran posed unanticipated challenges for the Palestinians. Prior to 1979, the PLO was a far stronger actor than the Iranian opposition. Khomeinist factions stood to benefit from the Palestinians' enhanced knowledge of guerilla warfare and experience operating an insurgent movement. After the Iranian Revolution, however, the clerics' unlikely accumulation of state power altered their political relationship with the PLO and recast the Palestinians as the weaker of the two actors; with the machinery of a massive, oil-rich nation suddenly at his full disposal, Khomeini no longer needed the Palestinians. Although Arafat was ultimately unable to resolve the hostage crisis and garner US recognition of the PLO, the Palestinians' success securing both the release of thirteen hostages in November 1979 and the release of the bodies of the eight US servicemen from Iran in May 1980 was no insignificant feat. The release of the bodies of the thirteen commandos killed at Desert One also appears to be the last development of the Iran hostage crisis over which the PLO plausibly exerted influence. While the Carter administration did list the PLO and Capucci as "traditional third-party channels" to revive last-ditch efforts to force the Ayatollah's hand as late as September 1980 (three months before the before the hostage crisis cost Carter re-election), it is entirely unknown whether actions were taken towards engaging Arafat at this point.⁹²

So long as the structural determinants of the Cold War bipolar balance of power were present, actors outside of the Western bloc who were willing to advocate for American interests provided a tactical advantage to the US. As I have argued, the value of the PLO during the Iran hostage crisis derived specifically from the fact that it was *not* a US ally. Ultimately, US security interests in post-revolutionary Iran were pursued not in spite of but necessarily because of the United States' reliance on a particularly strange bedfellow. By aligning with Arafat during the Iran hostage crisis, the Carter administration went far beyond eschewing the trademark US policy not to negotiate with "terrorists"—it encouraged "terrorists" to negotiate on its behalf.

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⁹² Central Intelligence Agency, "US Negotiating Options and Hostage Trials," September 10, 1980.

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